

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES
SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

ROLE OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (QMS) FOR EFFECTIVE REGULATORY COMPLIANCE

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Abstract:

Present day the biggest challenge faced by the pharmaceutical manufacturers is experiencing inspectional Food and Drug administration (FDA) 483's, warning letters, import alerts and notice of violations from the regulatory authorities. The USFDA's inspectional outcome has uncovered the retesting of drug ingredients that had failed quality testing, failure to establish corrective and preventive action following an investigation, procedural lapses etc. All these regulatory non-compliances triggered the FDA to issue warning letters, with holding of the product approval or plant shut-down because the US regulator has perceived violations to be of serious significance. Most experts warn that quality systems should focus on sustainability issues and assume that quality problems and regulatory non-compliances will be reduced as a result of the organized way of thinking, transparency, documentation and continuous evaluation of Quality Management System (QMS). QMS is a set of coordinated activities to direct and control an organization in order to continually improve the effectiveness and efficiency of its performance. It is designed and implemented to emphasize continuous improvement for state of compliance. QMS starts with recognizing that customers play a significant role in defining requirements as inputs and monitoring of customer satisfaction is necessary to evaluate and validate whether customer requirements have been met. QMS also lives in a dynamic regulatory environment of the registration and compliance requirements of global markets as well as inspections. As QMS is related to regulatory compliance and continuous inspection readiness, it shall maximize benefit to the organization by improving quality, increasing the yield, cutting costs and finally curbing FDA 483's, warning letters and import alerts. The article details about the significance of QMS and its modules for effective regulatory compliance.

Keywords: Inspectional FDA 483's, warning letters, CAPA, QMS.

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Please cite this article in press Bodige Sai Prasanna et al., *Role Of Quality Management System (QMS) For Effective Regulatory Compliance* .,Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12 (01).

INTRODUCTION:

The changing regulatory environment

In a Science Board Meeting held in November 2001, FDA raised some concerns regarding the efficiency of the pharmaceutical industry. The factors contributing to this situation were identified as follows:

- Pharmaceuticals are complex, multivariate physicochemical systems that are
 - Often treated (during development) as univariate systems (one-factor-at-a-time, trial- and-error experimentation)
 - Physical properties of materials normally not well characterized
 - Equipment selection based on tradition
 - Process factors are not well understood
- Development is done under time crunch
- Post approval changes require regulatory oversight

It was said that a *higher efficiency* is required in order to provide high quality drugs to the market in a timely manner, to successfully take advantage of the new drug development opportunities offered by advances in chemistry and biology. In addition, one should also ensure the optimal utilization of public and private resources to meet the growing health care needs and, last but not least, to obtain global competitiveness for the pharmaceutical industry.

The consequences are that the status quo is no longer tenable and that the pharmaceutical manufacturing could be much better. Furthermore, it is claimed that traditional metrics hide poor performance, and that compliance infrastructures are not economic. Currently, utilization levels are judged to be down to 15 percent or less, and costs in terms of quality are in excess of 20 percent.

The agency's conclusions were that often processes are transferred that are neither fully understood nor capable of being so at commercial scales. Also, there is a lack of scientific basis for deeper process understanding. Further, the pharmaceutical manufacturers fall short in the ability of a process to be 'right the first time' (e.g. pro-active quality management, six sigma approach)

Under the umbrella of the GMP for the 21st century initiative, the FDA started an international co-operation to find answers to the current situation covering the following topics:

- A science based approach
- Risk management
- QSIT (Quality System Inspection Technique)
- PAT (Process Analytical Technology)

QSIT and PAT

The Quality System Inspection Technique moves the FDA from reviewing all documentation to a system-based inspection covering the following six subsystems:

- Quality system
- Facilities and equipment system
- Production system
- Packaging and labeling system
- Laboratory controls system
- Materials system

Scientific and technological advances in the area of process analytical chemistry, engineering, and multivariate data analysis offer new opportunities for improving the overall efficiencies of drug development, manufacturing and regulatory processes. Although for many years the pharmaceutical community has recognized the need for improvements in these areas, little progress has been made. Therefore FDA forced the development of PAT (Process Analytical Technology). PAT is a model to facilitate the discussion on of emerging regulatory science issues in pharmaceutical manufacturing. PAT provides an opportunity to move from the current "testing to document quality" paradigm to a "Continuous Quality Assurance" paradigm that can improve the ability to ensure quality that was "built-in" or was "by-design" – the ultimate realization of the true spirit of GMP.

It is the expectation of the industry that these initiatives will result in improved product quality, reduced manufacturing cycle times, reduced laboratory testing burdens and costs.

QMS combining ISO and GMP

Overall, there is a clear tendency of authorities towards Quality Management Systems (QMS), as already outlined in some new guidelines, e.g. in ICH Q7a, Section 2.11 "*Each manufacturer should establish, document, and implement an effective system for managing quality that involves the active participation of management and appropriate manufacturing personnel*".

Finally, ISO 9002 already stated in the introduction: "*It is emphasized that the quality system requirements specified in this International Standard are complementary – not alternative - to the technical (product) specified requirements*".

As early as 1997 a guideline on the integration of the GMP requirements with the QMS requirements, issued by CEFIC/APIC, was available for the API manufacturers.

Introduction to the old APIC version (excerpt)

Because the pharmaceutical industry has traditionally focused upon the application of Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP), it has been slow to consider the potential benefits to be gained by implementing an EN ISO 9001 Quality Management System (QMS).

Over the last few years the global pharmaceutical market has undergone significant change, forcing pharmaceutical companies, more than ever before, to focus on customer needs and upon their own internal efficiency in order to continue to compete effectively.

With this in mind CEFIC commissioned a working group of experts drawn from several major Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (API) producers to prepare a practical, user-friendly guidance document integrating current GMP requirements into the EN-ISO 9001 QMS framework. To achieve this the working group have taken relevant features from the August 1996 CEFIC/EFPIA publication "Good Manufacturing Practice for Active Ingredients Manufacturers" and combined these with the relevant complementary requirements of EN-ISO 9001 "Quality Systems: Model for quality assurance in design, development, production, installation and servicing". It was intended that these Guidelines would be applicable to all APIs.

To facilitate understanding of this composite guidance document it is important for the reader to be aware of the following points:

- EN-ISO 9001 is a generic, business-focused standard that supports the effective management of quality to an internationally recognized level of best practice. It is flexible in that it specifies what is to be achieved, but allows each company freedom to determine, and justify, how these requirements are achieved. In contrast, GMP is an industry-specific standard prescribing what should be done to ensure product safety and efficacy. Thus, EN-ISO 9001 benefits the business by ensuring the quality of the management system, while GMP ensures that quality is built during the whole manufacturing and control process and that regulatory requirements are met.
- Although there is inevitably some overlap between the requirements of a QMS and GMP they are, in fact, highly complementary. This view is supported by a statement in the introduction to the PIC (Pharmaceutical Inspection Convention, now called PIC/S) GMP Guideline which refers to "... a correctly implemented system of Quality Assurance incorporating GMP ...", and by the wording of the introduction in ISO itself which points out that ".....

this international standard is complementary - not alternative - to the technical (product) specified requirements".

- The interrelationship between EN-ISO 9001 and API GMP is illustrated in this guidance document by a matrix cross-referencing the main QMS elements and GMP requirements.
- To be effective the QMS should have the visible and ongoing support of top management.
- To fully benefit the company the QMS should involve all staff whose activities influence quality, have a clear and unambiguous continuous improvement focus, and incorporate relevant, realistic performance measures with emphasis on reducing failure costs, and satisfying (internal and external) customer needs.
- The quality manual occupies the highest level in the document hierarchy. It overviews and acts as a directory to the QMS, capturing the unique character of the company.
- An effective QMS has a minimum of paperwork, and should constantly question the need for the existing documents. In contrast, a bureaucratic and inefficient QMS will arise if the Standard is misinterpreted, and incorrectly applied.

Safety, health and the environment were not specifically addressed. However, it was widely acknowledged that implementation of a robust QMS provides a sound basis for the future development of such an Integrated Management System.

Changes of the relevant GMP/ISO requirements

In the meantime the GMP as well as the QMS requirements have changed. For this reason the 1998 APIC guideline needs to be updated.

Changes to the GMP requirements

API manufacturers no longer need to follow GMPs as defined in e.g. 21 CFR Part 210/211, or draft versions of API guidance documents. The new ICH guideline Q7a "Good Manufacturing Practice for Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients" has some fundamentally different GMP requirements, and specifically applies to the manufacture of APIs for use in drug (medicinal) products. The guide covers APIs manufactured by chemical synthesis, extraction, cell culture/fermentation, by recovery from natural sources, or by any combination of these processes.

DISCUSSION**QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM****1.1 General Requirements**

Companies perform many activities besides manufacturing of APIs, such as development,

marketing, purchasing, warehousing and distribution. All these activities are processes which are required to be managed in a systematic manner. Therefore, the company shall establish, document and implement within its organization a Quality Management System that is designed to continually improve its effectiveness as required in section 2 (Quality Management) of ICH Q7a. Top management is called to establish a customer oriented organization:

- By defining the systems and processes that can be managed and improved in effectiveness and efficiency,
- Acquiring and using process data and information on a continuing basis,
- Directing progress towards continual improvement,
- Using suitable methods to evaluate process improvement.

Although ICH Q7a defines which part of the production process is subject to GMP (introduction of the 'API Starting Material') it is not advisable to limit the implementation of the QMS to these production steps; it should be extended to the entire company. From this perspective all regulatory and GMP activities of a company are captured by the Quality Management System.

An important part of the Quality Management System is made up of the Change Control procedures which represent the interface between the company, GMP, the authorities and customers, if applicable.

When a company decides to outsource activities it should ensure control over the outsourced process(es) and/or activities.

API material manufactured for use in clinical trials as described in section 19 of ICH Q7a (development) shall be fully integrated into the Quality Management System even if other GMP standards are to be applied.

The performance of the Quality Management System is the responsibility of every person involved in all activities related to the company's API business.

1.2 Documentation

1.2.1 General

A documentation system remains a fundamental component of a Quality Management System. The objective of such documentation is to identify and describe what should be in place. The documentation system is an essential tool to keep all

processes in a state of control.

Top management should define the documentation required to run a Quality Management System and to support effective and efficient operation of the processes. It should include:

- Top management's commitment to quality,
- A quality manual (see 1.2.2),
- Documented procedures,
- Documents and records needed for an efficient QMS.

The minimum extent of the documentation, especially regarding Master Production Instructions (section 6.4 of ICH Q7a) and laboratory documentation (section 11.1 of ICH Q7a), needed for compliance with GMP regulations is described in more detail in ICH Q7a.

The documentation created to run a Quality Management System and to comply with GMP requirements should fulfill criteria in respect of:

- Functionality,
- User friendliness,
- Structure of company's documentation system,
- Managing knowledge,
- Interfaces with other departments and, if applicable, with customers.

It is necessary to designate and document a rationale for the point at which production of the API begins ('API Starting Material'). In addition critical production steps should be identified, as should critical control points and parameters within the production of APIs. The company's overall approach to validation and change control procedures should be documented.

All quality-related activities should be recorded at the time of performance.

Deviations from established procedures should be documented and explained and/or investigated, a complaint and recall procedure has to be in place. Contract manufacturing (including laboratories) needs to be carefully managed, e.g. evaluation, assessment and documentation (including quality agreement). All (GMP) activities and responsibilities have to be defined in writing.

1.2.2 Quality Manual

The basic document of a Quality Management System is the quality manual. Although it is up to the company to decide the level of detail, the quality manual should be made as comprehensive as possible. The main elements to be incorporated include:

- The scope (see section IV, 3. Structure of a Quality Manual, section 4.1),
- The quality commitment,

- A description of the main processes,
- Their interactions and
- The description of major responsibilities.

1.2.3 Control of documents

All documents and records required by the QMS are subject to an appropriate control. A documented procedure shall be established to define the controls:

- Drafting, review, approval (Quality Unit at a minimum for GMP related documents) and up-date of documents,
- Handling and control of changes to documents (version control) including P & ID (Piping & Instrumentation Diagram) schemes,
- Handling, control and internal distribution of external documents,
- Withdrawal and prevention of unintended use of obsolete documents.

Details of a documentation system needed from a GMP perspective are given in ICH Q7a, section 6.1. It is a regulatory expectation that the impurity profile is checked at appropriate intervals against the registration dossier, e.g. as part of the Product Quality Review.

1.2.4 Control of records

Records provide evidence of conformity to requirements. They should be legible, readily identifiable and retrievable. A documented procedure should define the control needed for identification, storage, protection, retrieval, retention time and disposition.

The control of records includes hard copies as well as electronically stored data.

Records should be established, at least for raw materials, intermediates, labelling, packaging materials, batch production, laboratory data, including Certificates of Analysis and stability data, calibration, distribution, complaints and returns. A procedure for the review of batch production and laboratory records is required.

2. Management Responsibility:

2.1 Management commitment

Top management should provide evidence of its commitment to the development and implementation of the Quality Management System (QMS) and continual improvement of its effectiveness by:

- communicating to the organization the importance of meeting customer as well as regulatory (GMP) and legal requirements, including environmental, health and safety aspects,
- applying risk management,
- establishing the quality policy,

- ensuring that quality objectives are established,
- conducting management reviews,
- maintaining appropriate conditions throughout the organization for processes and systems,
- ensuring the availability of resources, particularly enough manpower, suitably trained.

2.2 Customer focus

Top management should make sure that customer (external and/or internal) needs and requirements are clearly understood so that, when fulfilled, they will lead to customer satisfaction.

Consequently, this calls for close communication with the customer throughout the whole co-operation including, at least, notification to the customer (e.g. dosage form manufacturer) of significant process changes (see also QMS 5.3) in a timely manner before implementation of the change and appropriate complaint management.

2.3 Quality policy

Top management should ensure that a clear commitment to complying with (regulatory and GMP) requirements and to continually improve the effectiveness of the Quality Management System is a key element. This should be explained in the quality policy. Furthermore, criteria affecting the efficiency of the system should be identified and evaluated.

Quality objectives should be based on the quality policy which is closely coupled with company operational planning. This should include a statement addressing environmental, health and safety obligations.

Measures have to be initiated to ensure that the key statements of the quality policy become part of the daily business. Therefore, the quality policy needs to be communicated to and understood at all levels within the organization. Quality is the responsibility of all persons involved in a process.

To cope with inevitable changes that occur in and around the organization, the quality policy should be reviewed for continuing suitability. The responsibility for these activities is clearly allocated to top management.

2.4 Planning

2.4.1 Quality objectives

Top management should make sure that quality objectives are known and widely used at all levels within the organization. By doing so, employees will identify with and become fully involved in reaching the agreed objectives. The quality objectives should be measurable and consistent with the quality policy. The “SMART” criteria

(S=Specific, M=Measurable, A=Achievable, R=Relevant, T=Time- framed) should be applied to establish quality objectives.

2.4.2 Quality Management System planning

Top management should ensure that the planning of the QMS is carried out in order to meet the requirements as defined in 4.1 (ISO) as well as the quality objectives. They should ensure that the integrity of the Quality Management System is maintained. Changes for system improvement should not impair the effectiveness and efficiency of the QMS.

Planning may be driven by e.g. strategies and organizational objectives, by customer needs, by regulatory requirements, by the intended use of the API, or by risk management. This may give rise to, e.g. skill and knowledge requirements, allocation of task responsibilities, resources (financial and infrastructure), performance metrics, contingency plans.

2.5 Responsibility, authority and communication

2.5.1 Responsibility and authority

Top management should make sure that responsibilities and competences (authorities) are defined for all profiles and communicated to all levels within the organization. There should be a quality unit (QU) independent of production, and that fulfills both quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) responsibilities.

2.5.2 Management representative

Top management should appoint a member of management who, irrespective of other responsibilities, is responsible and authorized:

- To make sure that processes needed for the Quality Management System are established, implemented and maintained,
- To report to top management on the performance of the Quality Management System and any need for improvement,
- To ensure the promotion of awareness of customer requirements throughout the organization. The responsibility of a management representative can include liaison with external parties on matters relating to the Quality Management System.

2.5.3 Internal communication

Top management should ensure that appropriate communication processes are established within the organization and that communication takes place regarding the effectiveness of the Quality Management System. This should include the communication of GMP and regulatory requirements as appropriate to each level in the organization.

Quality issues should be considered as a standard

topic on the agenda of all appropriate meetings as well as on the company's intranet website(s).

Procedures should exist for notifying responsible management in a timely manner of quality critical situations.

2.6 Management review

2.6.1 General

Top management should review the organization's Quality Management System at predefined intervals, to ensure its continuing suitability, adequacy and effectiveness. This review has to include assessing opportunities for improvement and the need for changes to the QMS, including the quality policy and the quality objectives.

The review should also cover environmental, health and safety aspects. Records of management reviews are to be maintained.

2.6.2 Review input

The input to top management review comprises a consolidation of the available data as a basis for their decision-making process. These data include, but are not limited to:

- audit observations / results (internal and external audits as well as inspections by authorities),
- supplier qualification,
- product conformity (product quality review),
- customer feedback,
- process performance, e.g. key performance indicators (KPI),
- status of corrective and preventive actions (CAPA),
- follow-up actions from previous management reviews,
- changes that could affect the Quality Management System,
- recommendations for improvement.

2.6.3 Review output

The output from the management review should include any decisions and actions taken relating to:

- continual improvement of the effectiveness of the QMS and its processes,
- continual improvement of product relating to customer requirements,
- resources (in relation to time, money and manpower) needed.

3. Resource Management

Resource management comprises provision of resources, infrastructure, human resources and the work environment.

3.1 Provision of resources

The top management has to determine and provide the resources needed:

- To implement and maintain the Quality Management System and continually improve its effectiveness,
- To enhance customer satisfaction by meeting defined requirements and specifications (including compliance with regulatory requirements),
- To maintain equipment and facilities and
- To adequately train and educate the employees.

Provision of resources is the responsibility of top management and has to be included into the budgeting and investment processes. These processes have to be defined in writing.

When using external resources such as contract manufacturers (including laboratories), they are expected to provide sufficient resources as described in this chapter. The external provision of resources should be ruled by contract.

3.2 Human resources

3.2.1 General

The top management has to provide an adequate number of personnel qualified by appropriate education, training, and/or experience to perform work and meet the requirements.

If the company's performance indicators (such as timelines for calibration due dates, deviation / investigation handling, testing, release) can constantly not be achieved in such a way as to run the QMS processes properly, the adequacy of the human resources should be reconsidered.

3.2.2 Competence, awareness and training

Competence, awareness and training are ensured through top management by:

- Implementing an adequate and effective organization,
- Determining the necessary competence and education for personnel performing work affecting quality of product and processes,
- Issuing job descriptions and qualifications for all functions throughout the organization,
- Training provided regularly by qualified individuals covering, at a minimum, the particular operations the employee performs and GMP as it relates to the employee's functions,
- evaluating the effectiveness of the training periodically, such as by
 - testing on the content of procedures
 - observing the employee performing the task(s)
 - checking the accuracy of the work and results
- Ensuring that personnel are aware of the relevance

and importance of their activities and how they contribute to the achievement of the quality objectives,

- maintaining appropriate records of education, training, skills and experience.

3.3 Infrastructure

Top management has to ensure that the organization determines, provides and maintains the infrastructure needed to conduct operations (e.g. manufacturing, testing and support) according to contemporary standards.

Infrastructure comprises buildings (including utilities and workspaces), equipment and computerized systems.

Buildings have to:

- Be located, designed, and constructed to facilitate cleaning, maintenance, and operations as appropriate to the type and stage of manufacture,
- Provide adequate space for the orderly placement of equipment and materials to prevent mix-ups and contamination,
- Provide adequate cleaning, washing and toilet facilities,
- Provide laboratory facilities separate from production,
- Provide adequate lighting in all areas to facilitate cleaning, maintenance, and proper operations,
- Provide areas for the storage of all materials under appropriate conditions (e.g., temperature and humidity),
- Provide adequate laboratory facilities for the quality unit,
- Be properly maintained and repaired,
- Provide separate areas for eating, drinking and smoking,
- Contain the necessary utilities (such as HVAC, water, gases etc.) in order to perform the relevant production operations.

Equipment should be:

- Of appropriate design, adequate size and suitably located for its intended use in order to facilitate cleaning, sanitization (where appropriate), and maintenance,
- Constructed so that surfaces that contact raw materials, intermediates, or APIs do not alter the quality of the intermediates and APIs beyond the official or other established specifications.

Computerized systems should be:

- Of appropriate design and adequate capacity,
- equipped with the necessary software programmes,
- maintained (such as programme updates or

exchange of hardware components),

- Safe against loss of data.

The infrastructure has to meet all legislative requirements laid down by regulatory authorities (safety issues, occupational health problems, environmental aspects, etc.).

3.4 Work environment

Top management should ensure that the work environment has a positive influence on motivation, satisfaction and performance of people in order to enhance the performance of the organization. Elements to be considered for a suitable work environment are:

- Creative work methods to enhance the potential of the employees,
- Use of protective equipment,
- Ergonomics,
- Sufficient workspaces as well as a suitable location,
- Opportunities for social interaction,
- Suitable heat, humidity, light and air flow,
- hygiene, cleanliness, noise, vibration and pollution. Full account should be taken of regulatory requirements.

4. Product Realization (Manufacturing Operations)

The product realization includes all the different value adding activities for the realization of product, starting from customer requirements up to shipment of product to the customer in the mutually agreed quality.

The realization process consists of different activities such as planning of the product realization, customer-related issues, design and development, purchasing, production, service provision and control of monitoring and measuring devices.

This chapter is the part of the document where most of the requirements of ICH Q7a related to manufacturing are applicable.

4.1 Planning of the product realization

The planning of the product realization should be in line with the QMS requirements of the other processes. All responsibilities of the different production activities should be defined in writing (ICH Q7a: 2.30). Process equipment, including laboratory equipment, is an important part in the planning of product realization. Equipment should be of adequate design and appropriately qualified before use in manufacturing of APIs or intermediates (ICH Q7a: 5.16). Schedules and procedures should be established for the preventive maintenance of equipment (ICH Q7a: 5.20). In addition, established cleaning procedures prevent contamination or carry-over (ICH Q7a: 5.21-5.25).

Where computerized systems are used in a GMP relevant process, hardware and software should be appropriately qualified and validated on the basis of the criticality of the system (ICH Q7a: 5.40-5.42). Changes to any equipment (including computer systems and laboratory equipment) should be done under a defined change control system to maintain the qualified status (ICH Q7a: 5.45, 5.47). All activities described above are subject to risk management.

Material in product realization should be defined by appropriate specifications, especially if the quality of the API is affected. Acceptance criteria should be established (ICH Q7a: 6.17 and 8.10-8.14) to control processes. All activities from material receipt to sampling and testing against defined specification and storage and release for use or rejection should be well defined (ICH Q7a: 7.10).

To prove the capability of the product realization process, the equipment should be qualified and the production process validated, where appropriate, following the requirements given in ICH Q7a Chapter 12.

Activities not covered by the manufacturers QMS, such as contract manufacturing (incl. laboratories), activities of brokers or distribution, a written contract should define in detail Quality responsibilities of each party (ICH Q7a: 16.10, 16.12). All companies involved in the product realization process should comply with the GMP requirements as defined in Q7a.

4.2 Customer-related processes

The responsibilities for all production activities should be defined in writing (ICH Q7a: 2.30).

Critical changes in the realization process of the intermediate or the API should be evaluated and customers should be notified before implementation of significant changes (ICH Q7a: 13.16/17, see also QMS 5.3) if mutual agreed.

A written procedure should ensure the investigation of all quality related customer complaints (ICH Q7a: 15.10).

4.3 Design and development

The design and development process comprises planning, determination, review and verification of inputs and outputs and the control of changes. To achieve a robust manufacturing process it is mandatory to perform all of the above-mentioned steps.

For all further details and activities regarding GMP for new chemical entities see ICH Q7a, section 19 (APIs for Clinical Trials).

4.4 Purchasing

Purchased items which could impact final product quality should be purchased to defined requirements according to written procedures from an approved supplier. There should be written procedures describing receipt, initial visual check of labels and containers, identification, quarantine, storage, handling, sampling, testing and approval or rejection of materials.

Suppliers should be selected on the basis of their ability to supply the items and their performance. Supply chain and/or manufacturer qualification for critical raw materials, utilities and services is mandatory. Particular attention should be paid to:

- Changes to the supply chain and/or the manufacturing processes which could impact the organization's final product, e.g. changes in method might impact product purity or performance.
- Purchasing documentation, which may include data relating to the suppliers and/or manufacturer's Quality Management Systems e.g. Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP), Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP). Purchasing data would also be expected to include Certificates of Analysis / Conformity.
- Verifying that the product is as ordered, so as to prevent cross-contamination or product disruption.

Receipt of a material prompts the following actions:

- Initial visual check of labels and containers to verify correct material and that there is no evidence of damage, tampering or contamination.
- Assignment of a distinctive code or batch number.
- Identification of the status.
- Bulk deliveries in non-dedicated tankers require assurance of the absence of cross-contamination.
- Materials are kept under quarantine and should not be mixed with existing stocks until approved.

Sampling and testing:

- Sampling is to be performed at defined locations and by procedures designed to prevent contamination.
- Containers from which samples have been withdrawn should be marked.
- Samples should be representative of the batch of material from which they are taken.
- Each batch should be tested for conformance with specifications unless the supplier's Certificate of Analysis has been verified as accurate.
- As a minimum requirement an identity test on each batch is mandatory.

- Processing aids, hazardous or highly toxic raw materials, and other special materials do not need to be tested if a Certificate of Analysis shows that these materials conform to established specifications or are shown to be suitable for the intended use.

Approval or rejection of material:

- Material that conforms to specifications may be approved by the quality unit.
- Rejected material should be identified and controlled under a quarantine system designed to prevent their unauthorized use in manufacturing.

Storage and handling:

- Materials should be handled and stored in a manner to prevent degradation, contamination, and cross-contamination.
- Placement of stored material should allow easy cleaning and inspection.
- Stored material should be used on the basis of the first-in first-out principle.
- Materials should be re-evaluated after prolonged storage to determine their suitability for use.

4.5 Production and service provision

Production and service provision should be systematically planned and controlled to predetermined conditions derived from comprehensive process understanding (e.g. specifications, process parameters, contents and scope of service, operating procedures). Operating under these conditions would reduce the potential for non-conformities, deliver material that is fit for use in the customer's application and provide the basis for continual process improvement.

In order to reduce costs of failure and to control the production process, all steps (if necessary) should be adequately monitored. The requirement of process validation applies only to critical production steps and is documented evidence that the process can be performed effectively and reproducibly.

Product conformity should be continually maintained throughout the entire supply chain by appropriate measures for identification, handling, packaging, storage and protection.

Traceability depends on the nature of the processing, e.g. bulk silos and storage tanks, continuous processing and requires appropriate concepts (e.g. batch, time or volume based). Identification and traceability are imperative by regulatory requirements.

In the special case of contract manufacturing specified control conditions should be observed and deviations notified to the customer according to the agreement.

ICH Q7a items to be considered for production and service provision are listed below:

- Document control, pre-approved manufacturing procedures, batch record review and handling of deviations,
- Qualification, process, analytical and cleaning validation,
- Change control,
- Production activities (chemical as well as biotech) such as in-process controls, blending, recovery of materials, hygiene, calibration, cleaning, sanitation, maintenance, contamination control as well as packaging and labelling of APIs and intermediates,
- Utilities (e.g. air, piping), water treatment and containment,
- design and construction of facilities and process equipment,
- sampling (including retention samples), testing and release of materials, intermediates and APIs,
- storage and distribution of materials, intermediates and APIs,
- stability of APIs and intermediates, where appropriate,
- returns,
- APIs for clinical trials and their appropriate controls.

4.6 Control of monitoring and measuring devices

The suitability of devices used to monitor product characteristics for the intended purpose should be confirmed, and they should be checked, calibrated and regularly maintained.

This includes computerized systems, laboratory instruments, reference materials, standard analytical solutions and buffer solutions used for process controls.

5. Measurement, Analysis and Improvement (Evaluation Activities)

5.1 Deviation Investigation

The Quality Management System should ensure that deviations from established procedures are identified and recorded. Incidents that could affect the quality of API or the reliability of records or test results should be investigated. The Quality Unit is responsible for making sure that critical deviations are investigated and resolved. The Quality Management System should specify the responsibilities for all functions involved in the investigation and resolution of deviations.

5.2 Product Quality Review (Annual Product Review)

The Product Review itself is a GMP requirement and

should be conducted annually, or on another routine basis, as justified, to evaluate process consistency through reviews of:

- critical in-process control and critical API test results (Q7a 2.50);
- all batches that failed to meet established specification(s) (Q7a 2.50);
- all critical deviations or non-conformities and related investigations (Q7a 2.50);
- any changes made to the processes or analytical methods (Q7a 2.50);
- results of the stability monitoring program (Q7a 2.50);
- all quality-related returns, complaints and recalls (Q7a 2.50);
- adequacy of corrective actions (Q7a 2.50);
- the current impurity profile versus the established impurity profile.

The cumulative effects of changes to systems and processes should also be reviewed periodically to determine if there is a need to revalidate. The Product Review may be used to evaluate process performance with respect to validation.

5.3 Change Management

A continual improvement-focused QMS is, by definition, a dynamic entity. The introduction to this publication stresses the need to adequately document quality critical systems to ensure uniformity and understanding. Changes are, therefore, intimately linked with documentation and its control. Quality critical changes should be comprehensively planned, carefully controlled, and fully documented. All relevant stakeholders, including regulatory authorities and customers where appropriate, should be involved and/or notified, depending upon the nature and significance of the proposed change.

Implementation of changes

- All documents affected by the change should be identified and revised accordingly.
- Changes to documents should be reviewed and approved by the same functions that performed the original review and approval, unless specifically designated otherwise. The designated functions should have access to pertinent background information upon which to base their review and approval.
- Where appropriate, the nature of the change(s) should be identified in the revised document or attachments. However, it is advantageous to incorporate a brief summary of previous changes in the current version of the document.
- Relevant changes in documents previously submitted to regulatory authorities and/or

customers should also be notified.

- Any operator training needed should be satisfactorily completed (and recorded).
- Several batches of API produced following implementation of the change should be extensively evaluated.
- Changes resulting from corrective and/or preventive action should be documented and adequately controlled.
- Changes to existing quality critical activities should only be introduced once validation is completed, documented and approved.

Periodic Review of Cumulative Changes

Validated processes (including computerized systems) should be monitored and/or periodically evaluated, and previous changes assessed, to determine whether there is a need for revalidation.

5.4 Audits

Internal quality audits, incorporating ISO and GMP requirements, provide a regular and systematic way of obtaining objective evidence about how the QMS is functioning. They are an effective means of highlighting activities requiring attention and are, therefore, a means of driving continual improvement. This approach should be achieved through the use of documented procedures for planning, implementation and follow-up of internal quality audits to verify compliance with documented QMS activities, quality manual claims, and GMP and other regulatory requirements. Since many GMP deficiencies are the result of a weakness in, or failure of, part of the QMS, an effective internal quality audit system will go a long way towards ensuring regulatory compliance, and will facilitate continual inspection readiness.

- Internal quality audits should be scheduled as part of an ongoing QMS internal audit programme covering the scope of the quality system documented in the quality manual. The frequency with which different parts are audited should be determined on the basis of importance to overall QMS performance, i.e. activities with known weaknesses should be audited more frequently.
- Internal quality audits should be planned, performed, recorded and followed up by suitably trained staff who are independent of the area being audited. Internal quality auditors should be experienced in QMS and GMP in order to perform audits which benefit the organization.
- It is the responsibility of the Quality Unit to make sure that internal quality audits are performed.

- Internal quality system audit findings should be discussed with the management unit responsible. Agreed, time-limited remedial actions should be recorded and followed up to completion and sign-off.
- The follow-up activities should verify the effectiveness of the corrective action taken.
- Output of the internal quality audit programme should be summarized and periodically submitted to top management as an integral part of the management review process.
- Further guidance for conducting quality system audits is provided in ISO 19011: 2002 (Guidelines for Quality Audit and/or Environment Management Systems Auditing)

5.5 Complaints

All customer complaints should be recorded, promptly investigated and reported in accordance with a written, approved procedure. Quality related complaints have GMP significance, and it is the responsibility of the Quality Unit to assure that these complaints are investigated and resolved. Records of complaints should be reviewed as part of the product quality review (annual product review) in order to identify trends and corrective and preventive actions.

5.6 Data Analysis

An integral part of successfully implementing an effective QMS is the need to identify, agree and use realistic criteria for routinely monitoring performance trends (KPI – Key Performance Indicators). These kinds of data are needed to support the Balanced Scorecard approach. Some general examples are provided below. The nature and emphasis of performance measures will, inevitably, vary from one company to another. Examples given below are not all-inclusive:

- Improvement initiatives ongoing and/or completed
- Quality failures e.g. cost of production failures per month
- Percentage on-time delivery to customer
- Failure costs per development project as % of project costs
- Controlled documents overdue for review
- Internal audit observation trends
- Customer complaints (numbers, response times)
- Recalls and other market withdrawals
- Laboratory errors and OOS results
- Process deviation frequency
- Staff training status
- Equipment breakdowns per month

CONCLUSION:

In the past, some organizations established QMS procedures and forms separately or on top of regular

operations management procedures in order to pass audits and get a required certification. Many older QMS processes focused on generating the paper trail necessary for evidence in a checklist-based certification process. However, the new ISO 9001:2008 QMS standards require more. The new standards are process-based versus checklist-based and require that a company walk auditors through normal every day processes demonstrating mechanisms that enforce disciplines dictated by the QMS requirements—disciplines that identify, manage and control any risk of missing quality goals throughout the entire product realization process. Instead of treating a QMS as a side initiative required for compliance, organizations can take a new look at their existing business processes and enterprise systems to optimize not just QMS compliance, but optimize the entire performance of business operations. Perhaps filling gaps where necessary and integrating systems with risk management, process control and quality management in mind. The improved procedures and processes will not only provide compliance, but will also reduce cost, improve product quality, and ultimately improve customer satisfaction and the bottom line.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The Authors are thankful to Sura Labs, Dilshukhnagar, Hyderabad for providing the necessary facilities for the research work.

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